

ISSUES OF TEACHING INTERPRETIVE READING IN THE EARLY STAGES OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION AMONG TURKIC PEOPLES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the issues of teaching primary school students interpretive reading in mother tongue lessons through the sources of Turkic folklore.

Introduction

Folklore works have been expressively read since ancient times, and expressive reading has held immense importance in our traditions, becoming deeply embedded in the very fabric of the people's life. For example, during festivals and weddings, poetic exchanges between young men and women were held, also known as "Guli surkh." Girls recited poems to boys, and boys to girls, presenting flowers along with them. They strove to respond with poems that were similar in meaning and harmony of tone. Such exchanges developed expressive reading abilities among young people and nurtured their spirituality. The role of expressive reading in folklore is especially evident in dramatic works. Clowns, comedians, and puppeteers created performances that were passed down orally from generation to generation as traditional folk theater. Oral dramas consisted of monologues and dialogues and were mostly satirical and humorous in nature. The performers of these oral dramas—comedians and entertainers—delivered them with great skill, clearly articulating words and successfully conveying the meaning of the work to the audience.

Main part

Since ancient times, games have played an important role in educating children. They help children become resourceful, skillful, agile, and healthy. Another important aspect is that games teach children to express their thoughts fluently, clearly, and beautifully, and to find expressions appropriate to the content. At first glance, there is a very simple yet extremely complex and aesthetically rich exercise in expressive reading. In the game, children try to imitate the voice of the "mother goose" in a manner similar to that of real mothers. In each round of the game, different children take on the role of the "mother goose." Thus, every child strives to choose and control their voice. The "geese" must say the word "We are afraid" in a sad and timid tone, and the word "of the wolf" with a sense of fear and anxiety. The "mother goose" should say the phrase "Fly, fly and come" in an encouraging and uplifting tone. The geese, gaining strength from her brave voice, must escape from the wolf. The poem embedded in this game plays an important role in developing expressive reading skills in children. In

conclusion, folklore works educate individuals of all ages—from preschool children to adults—and at the same time form and develop expressive reading skills and competencies.

The Importance of Genre-Specific Features in the Expressive Reading of Written Literary Works.

Literature is divided into epic, lyrical, dramatic, and lyric-epic types, and the expressive reading of works belonging to these categories differs accordingly. Especially in prose works, expressive reading requires considerable skill, because it plays an important role in identifying the artistic features of a literary work, the ideas it conveys, and the author's worldview. Before engaging in expressive reading of prose, it is necessary to determine the main idea of the text. First of all, the selection of the text must be approached with great care. A prose work chosen for expressive reading should be of high quality, possess significant artistic value, and at the same time serve educational purposes. The epic genre includes such forms as the short story, novella, and novel, and their genre-specific features must be taken into account during expressive reading. When reading a short story expressively, it is important to consider that it is a brief prose work reflecting only one aspect of human life. Although it may include the author's narration, descriptions of nature, dialogues, and characters' speech, it is still shorter than a novella or novel. In primary classes, students are provided with short stories, excerpts from longer works, and literary-scientific texts. For example:

"One day, when I tried to drive the calf out of the herd, it ran into the wheat field. In my haste, unable to find a stick, I pulled out the apricot sapling that my father had planted. Remembering this, I blushed. Later, I told my father about it and apologized. 'Now you must plant two trees: one to replace the one you pulled out, and one as your own contribution,' my father said."

This excerpt from Mahmud Murodov's story "*Bir tup sada*" must be read by the teacher using two different tones, since it contains both the narrator's voice and the father's character. In this story, the narrator and the main character are the same person—a child. The teacher should read the child's voice in a gentle yet lively tone, while the father's voice should be firm, yet calm and composed.

One of the factors ensuring successful classroom reading is selective reading. The teacher's explanation and demonstration of expressive reading are of great importance. Only a text that is read expressively can be fully understood. This, in turn, ensures conscious comprehension of the material read in class. A student can develop personal qualities only when they understand what the text is about. Furthermore, they realize the importance of reading in becoming a good person. To ensure conscious reading, it is necessary to clarify the connections between the text and the accompanying illustrations and to ask questions based on the text. The main principle of expressive reading is a deep understanding of the idea and artistic value of the text. The more a teacher works on their own speech while presenting the content, the more meaningful, precise, and understandable it becomes. Regular practice of expressive reading enriches students' speech and plays a key role in the formation of their language skills. Particular attention should be paid to speech technique, since expressive reading is closely related to oral speech. Therefore, both teachers and students should

continuously improve their oral skills through special exercises focused on breathing and diction. As a rule, the teacher reads the text first. For example:

"The leaves of the trees begin to turn golden. In the morning and evening breeze, they flutter like golden-winged birds. The waters, which flowed noisily and sometimes muddily throughout the summer, become calm and clear."

This passage should be read calmly and with enjoyment, as it is rich in artistic imagery. However, the following text should be read with a more solemn tone rather than enjoyment, because the first example is from a literary work, while the second is from a scientific-literary text:

"Navruz is a celebration of nature, an ecological holiday, a time of kindness, labor, and peace. Every year, on the eve of Navruz, a nationwide community effort is organized in our country. People of all ages go out into the streets, clean irrigation ditches, sweep the surroundings, whitewash trees, and plant various flowers."

It is clear that in expressive reading, the type and genre of a literary work play a significant role. Primary school students are often assigned to memorize poems as homework. During the memorization process, ensuring expressive reading independently depends on the student. However, it is not possible to immediately achieve expressive, emotional, and accurate speech while working independently on expressive reading and speech development. At the initial stage, a learner should be able to use their breathing and voice effectively while speaking, as well as check their ability to pronounce sounds correctly and clearly. At this point, knowledge of speech technique becomes essential. These skills are gradually taught to primary school students. Speech technique refers to the processes of reading and speaking, proper breathing, voice control, and pronunciation. According to its object and function, speech technique consists of four main components: voice, breathing, articulation, and diction. The speech technique of an expressive reader should reach the level of the art of verbal performance. Accordingly, mastering expressive reading involves three key aspects:

1. The ability to use breathing effectively during speech
2. Mastery of correct articulation and clear diction for each sound
3. Knowledge of standard literary pronunciation norms

Conclusion and discussion

These skills are taught at an elementary level to primary school students. Therefore, a teacher who instructs expressive reading must themselves be theoretically well-prepared. Breathing is one of the most important tools of expressive reading and is also essential for the human body.

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